

IMPORTANT ISSUES OF COOPERATION WITH PARENTS IN THE ORGANIZATION OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation: In this article, there are a number of interruptions in cooperation with parents in preschool education organizations, the opinions of our channel scholars, and general conclusions from foreign systems are highlighted in this article.

Keywords: Educator, China, Korea, cooperation with parents in preschool education organization, idea, family upbringing.

INTRODUCTION

It is possible to achieve positive results in the education of children thanks to skillfully combining the forms of working with parents in the preschool education organization in a team style and individually, and organizing pedagogical campaign work among the general population. Some of the most common forms of in preschool educational organizations staff's work in partnership with parents and families can be cited:

- one-on-one work with parents. Advanced pedagogical experiences show that this type of work is of great importance. In this case, the educator studies the personal characteristics of the family and the child and takes them into account in his educational work. In the experience of our pre-school education organizations, various forms of one-on-one work with parents have been identified; visit of the tutor to the family, conducting a conversation for the parents, giving them advice, familiarizing the parents with the life of in preschool educational organizations.

-work organized with parents as a team. These are group and general meeting of parents, school of parents, conferences, Saturdays, question-and-answer evenings.

- instructional works. This type of work is demonstrative, showing children's work, open house, pedagogical information stands, library for parents, a folder with materials on all issues of family education. - can show parents pedagogical training and others. In preschool educational organizations Cooperation with parents.

In order to ensure the comprehensive development of the child, the preschool educational organization can organize the following forms of interaction with parents:

- *taking into account parents' opinions about preschool education;
- *providing knowledge to parents on issues of early development;
- * involving parents to actively participate in the educational process;
- *it is possible to support the initiatives of parents to participate in the life of the institution.

The ancient Greek philosophers Plato and Aristotle put forward the idea that the society should take over the education of children, and the state should perform all the necessary work in the education process. They put forward the idea that the state should mainly deal with child education. But Eastern thinkers came to the conclusion that parents should be mainly involved in child education. With this, they paid great attention to the role of family education.

Before the children come to the preschool educational institution, the child learns the first signs of important culture and the most necessary skills in the family. Currently, some parents think that the attention to the child is strong, but the child does not reflect the strong attention in their imagination.

The fact that parents do not work together with in preschool educational organizations and neglect of their little children is one of the most pressing problems of today. Parents should be in constant contact with the educator, be interested in their children's abilities, needs and interests, and their readiness for school. Involvement of parents in preschool educational organizations is beneficial for the educator, the child and for themselves. Mutual respect, communication, culture and the importance of the child's interests are the basis for effective cooperation.

In foreign countries, the interest of their children is more important than their work. In Japan, motherhood is always the first priority for women.

In Korean preschool education, there are constant discussions with parents. At such meetings, the child's actions, his achievements, and teachers gave insights on how to organize effective education at home. Before going to each family, the educator should set a clear goal for himself, decide in advance what topic he will talk about. Questions to parents should be carefully thought out. The conversation should be structured in such a way that the educator and parents understand each other well, and a reliable relationship should be established between them.

Before visiting a family, the educator should have certain ideas about this family (character of parents, family relations, child's level of development). In order to gain the respect and trust of the parents, the educator first expresses his opinions and comments to the parents about the positive qualities of the child and how to organize the child's life at home, what to read and tell him stories, the child's daily routine, makes recommendations on the content and methods of educational work, such as involving him in family work, raising him in respect for adults. Of course, in the educator's work with the family, the child's age, capabilities, and characteristics are taken into account.

The following special forms of work are used in working with parents: interviews, consultations, visiting families, inviting some parents to kindergarten, using special memorabilia and mobile folders. The purpose of visiting the child's home is to get to know the family conditions, the child's behavior and interests, parents and family members, as well as to introduce parents to effective methods of child education and to study and publicize the family's positive experiences in child education.

The educator should go to the child's house not as an inspector, but as a friend, a helper in the difficult task of raising a child, and should treat family members with kindness and courtesy.

Parents or other family members are invited to the preschool educational institution in order for the teacher's recommendations and advice to the parents to be reliable. In this case, parents see how the child is doing his duty or how he is playing before going for a walk, they are sure of the children's learning and capabilities.

The purpose and content of the visit to the family should be reflected in the educator's plan and report, as well as in his diary. The tutor must visit each child's family at least twice a year.

The content of work with parents is diverse, and it is necessary to discuss some issues together. For example:

- the role of the family in raising children, laws on the duties of parents, preparing children for school;
- on the annual work plan of pre-school education institutions;
- issues related to the work of the parents' community are among them.

Forms of work such as groups of parents and general meetings, consultations, conferences, parents' evenings for discussing these issues as a team are included in the forms of team work.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth noting that parents' neglect of their children's education in preschool educational organizations leads to the child's interest, what direction he will go in the future, not knowing what love is, and putting the educator in the place of his mother. That is why he is in constant contact with in preschool educational organizations. should be. Parents should not neglect their children.

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